

DigiVet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

DENMARK WP3 workshop report

2023

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Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Overview of the DigiVet Project.....	4
Introduction	5
Exercise 1: Data availability and sharing.....	5
Denmark.....	5
UK.....	6
Sweden.....	6
Discussion on general challenges around data sharing.....	6
Exercise 2: Introduction to DigiVet tools	8
sdubcontrol.....	8
Potential use	8
Technical features.....	9
goldeneye.....	10
Potential use	10
General comments on goldeneye.....	10
Next steps	11
Appendices.....	12
Appendix 1: Participant affiliations.....	12
Appendix 2: DigiVet project partners and contact details.....	12
Appendix 3: Summarised challenges and strengths by country.....	13
Appendix 4: Participant information sheet and consent form	15

Executive Summary

The DigiVet project is studying how livestock data are currently used across the partner nations (Estonia, Norway, Denmark, Sweden and the United Kingdom; UK) and how technology, training, and regulatory frameworks might provide societal benefit by improving the public-interest uses of livestock data. As part of the project, a workshop was held in Copenhagen, Denmark to compare challenges in sharing data and knowledge relating to foodborne disease, including *Salmonella* Dublin (*S. Dublin*). This workshop was also used to present and discuss two digital tools that were created as part of the DigiVet project, as well as to receive feedback from stakeholders on their use.

A total of 27 participants and project members from 3 out of the 5 partner countries took part in the workshop in September 2023. The overall availability of *S. Dublin* data varied widely between the three countries, with Denmark having the strongest tradition for sharing of data as part of the national control programme. Whilst Sweden also has a national control programme for *S. Dublin*, there is currently little provision for sharing of sensitive data relating to test results between industry and academia. The UK does not currently have an active surveillance programme in place, so very little sharing of data at farm level occurs.

A number of challenges were identified, which can be broadly categorised into two themes. The first theme was the potential for information bias in the available data arising from the complexities in terms of selecting animals for sampling that are inherent to a national-level surveillance programme. This issue is particularly relevant to the UK, where *S. Dublin* surveillance is carried out passively, meaning that collection of data is reliant on submission of samples by farmers and veterinarians in response to clinical suspicion of disease. The second theme was identification of obstacles to more extensive sharing of data. This included concerns regarding data security and legal uncertainty regarding the status of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as relating to livestock data, which it was felt has restricted the extent of data sharing agreements.

The project team presented two digitalisation tools to the participants: the *sdbuscontrol* tool that allows stakeholders to examine potential implications of different control programmes, and the *goldeneye* tool that facilitates routine encryption of potentially sensitive data for safe storage and transfer (both tools are provided in the form of R/shiny packages). The participants were given time to experiment with the tools (with technical assistance provided by the project team where necessary) before feedback was elicited via breakout groups. For the *sdbuscontrol* package, a wide range of suggestions were obtained regarding widening the scope of the tool so that it is applicable to other surveillance programmes, as well as more technical suggestions for specific features such as the ability to reset parameters to their defaults. Feedback on the *goldeneye* tool primarily focussed on the potential utility of setting an end date for a project beyond which decryption would not be allowed. It was felt that this would be an extremely valuable mechanism of adding an additional level of security to data sharing agreements.

Overall, the workshop revealed that although historical attitudes and traditions with respect to sharing of data relating to foodborne disease differed among countries, future challenges relating to changing legal requirements and shifting attitudes to sharing sensitive data are likely to be similar. Some of these challenges can be partially mitigated by data digitalisation tools, although some of the legal challenges relating to GDPR have wider ramifications.

Overview of the DigiVet Project

Successful management of livestock disease contributes to a consistent supply of safe food for everyone in society. The use of data by industry, public services, and even the public at large is a key part of this veterinary public health mission. However, managing these data comes with many challenges: how should data collection be standardised, and who should have access to different aspects of these data? What risks are farmers exposed to by making their data publicly available? What data and processes need to be maintained to be able to effectively control shared threats to our supply of safe food within our increasingly international society?

The DigiVet project is studying how livestock data are currently used across the partner nations (Estonia, Norway, Denmark, Sweden and UK) and how technology, training, and regulatory frameworks might provide societal benefit by improving the public-interest uses of these data. The study includes workshops with stakeholders to map existing practices, and document the gaps, roadblocks, and opportunities for improvement. Three case studies cover foodborne disease, antimicrobial usage, and contagious diseases of livestock. Foodborne illnesses such as Salmonella are a serious public health issue, antimicrobial usage in livestock may be contributing to the developing antimicrobial resistance problem in human pathogens. Exotic and highly contagious livestock diseases such as African swine fever have the potential to devastate our national agricultural sectors. Each of these challenges has wide-reaching implications for society as a whole.

Meeting these challenges requires different approaches, but each are united by their dependence on similar sources of data to enable authorities to continually monitor the threat and respond quickly when required. Within the study we test the models and statistical data analytics that are used in each partner nation across the other geographic settings, investigating what approaches will work under which circumstances, and what needs to change to facilitate more effective use of the data. DigiVet will also investigate the risks associated with missing, sparse, or coarsely aggregated data, and evaluate the potential societal benefits of making better quality data more widely available.

Project website: https://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~jenright/digivet_website/index.html

The project is funded by Nordforsk: a body which funds Nordic research and cooperation.
<https://www.nordforsk.org/>

Introduction

The workshop summarised in this report took place at the University of Copenhagen and was designed to encourage discussion and co-learning among the stakeholders present. All participants were asked to read an information sheet and sign a consent form prior to the start of the workshop (see attached supplementary information).

This was the second of three workshops to be held during the course of Work Package 3. The aims of the workshop were to share experiences about the use of similar data between stakeholders from the UK, Denmark, and Sweden and to discuss the practical, ethical and governance issues surrounding the use of livestock data between industry and academic partners. Participants were also asked to give feedback on two data digitalisation tools developed in the DigiVet project (*sdubcontrol* and *goldeneye*).

The workshop was attended by 20 stakeholders from Denmark, Sweden and UK (see details in Appendix 1) and was facilitated by researchers at the James Hutton Institute in conjunction with partners at the University of Copenhagen.

Exercise 1: Data availability and sharing

In this exercise participants were divided into three mixed-country groups, and asked to discuss how data, particularly that relevant to *Salmonella* Dublin (*S. Dublin*), are shared within their country. Each country had different practices and the accessibility of data varied considerably.

Denmark

Since 2002 the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA, in Danish Fødevarestyrelsen [FVST]) have carried out a national surveillance, control and eradication programme for *S. Dublin* in cattle – details of relevant legislation are summarised in previous deliverables from this project so are not repeated here. Infected premises must undergo special handling requirements and may not move animals to uninfected premises. SEGES (see below) on behalf of the DVFA carry out statutory surveillance of bulk tank milk in all dairy herds four times a year and of blood samples taken at the abattoir in all non-dairy herds up to four times a year. Some non-dairy herds are sampled less than four times a year because they send animals for slaughter at a lower frequency, such as can be the case for heifer herds. Therefore, surveillance additionally includes blood sampling of live animals in heifer herds. If the heifer herd has a single supplier, then eight animals should be sampled once a year, while herds with mixed suppliers should sample eight animals twice a year. Additional samples may also be taken voluntarily by the farmer. Finally, culture samples from suspected cases of *Salmonella* spp. (based on clinical signs of disease) are mandatory and included in the surveillance. The resulting data are stored at SEGES farmers' association, which is a private non-profit advisory, test and research association cooperatively owned by 30,000 Danish farmers, including owners of around 15,000 cattle farms contributing to *S. Dublin* surveillance. SEGES bridges the gap between farmers and research in close cooperation with local agricultural advisory centres and is the main Danish supplier of professional knowledge for farmers as well as for food businesses, authorities, and agricultural colleges (<https://www.legvalue.eu/stakeholder-directory/seges-ps/>). There are different levels of data available, some of which are shared with the Danish central livestock register (CHR). Previously, any voluntary samples taken by farmers were included in determination of surveillance status, but as of 1st July 2021, voluntary samples are no longer included automatically.

Farmers can still enter these voluntary samples into the Danish Cattle Database (DCD), but not all farmers opt to do this. The current surveillance classification for each cattle property is publicly available at farm level via a web interface (<http://chr.fvst.dk>) but only the Danish government, SEGES, vets, and the farmer and farm advisors can see the actual test values. There was a perception of a strong and long-running collaboration between industry, government and academia in the management of the *S. Dublin* eradication programme.

UK

There are no *S. Dublin* eradication programmes in any of the UK devolved nations. Neither is there a statutory surveillance system for *S. Dublin* in cattle in the UK, but data are collected through passive surveillance. Salmonella is a statutory disease meaning any occurrence must be reported to the Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA). Because surveillance is passive, diagnostics depend on industry engagement through the farmer and the vet choosing to test for *Salmonella* spp..

Ultimately, any laboratory data collected are owned by the government agencies. There is no sharing of farm-level data, but rather anonymised data are published annually by the APHA (<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/651e952e5f7e68000dfabd8e/salmonella-animals-feed-great-britain-2022.pdf>). Data sharing often doesn't happen, in part because it is restricted by GDPR.

Sweden

Sweden has a zero-tolerance policy for *S. Dublin* and has a continuous and systematic surveillance programme at abattoirs, controlled by the Swedish Board of Agriculture. Whenever Salmonella is suspected in a herd, an investigation is made to verify its presence. If Salmonella is detected in samples from animals in the herd, tracing is performed to identify the source of infection and possible spread. In addition to the mandatory control of Salmonella, there is a voluntary control programme, with responsibility assigned to farmers' organizations. The national laboratory accesses results from the national surveillance programme, but these data are not made publicly available. Data from a voluntary dairy industry scheme covering the majority of dairy herds in Sweden are also not publicly available and data sharing between industry and the national laboratory is not straightforward, although pseudonymised data are made available for sharing with external stakeholders.

Discussion on general challenges around data sharing

Although data are available in varying formats within each country there are still challenges around sharing it more widely. There is ongoing discussion about who actually owns the data, the status of different kinds of data as well as the moral issue of how widely it should be shared, with whom, and for what purpose. If data are shared, how much detail should be openly accessible? What are the consequences to the various actors (farmers, vets etc.) should potentially sensitive data be made publicly available? An additional challenge in Denmark is the possibility that any data held by a university are potentially eligible to be requested for release under a freedom of information request; the possibility that this could occur with sensitive data such as *S. Dublin* test results (along with farm identifiers) is an ongoing concern.

Legal issues around new GDPR regulations have become more important in recent years. For instance, in the UK there has been discussion about whether or not data that identifies a farm through its County Parish Holding number counts as personal data, and consequently the degree of

sensitivity with which these data should be regarded. There is a perception by some in Denmark and Sweden that the uncertainty surrounding the applicability of GDPR regulations to livestock data has led to less data sharing than was previously possible based on a legal 'precautionary principle', despite that the current consensus in Denmark is that farm data are not subject to GDPR. Currently, data sharing agreements are frequently somewhat *ad hoc*, so there is potential for sharing data between different organisations in a more systematic way.

Ownership of *S. Dublin* data differs between countries. In the UK, samples from animals at the abattoir no longer belong to the farmer as there is no proof that the pathogen originated from a particular farm rather than being e.g. picked up en route to slaughter. In Denmark the animals still belong to the farmer, so although meat hygiene test results stay with the abattoir, serology results belong to the farmer and/or DVFA. In Sweden, positive results in the abattoir are reported back to the farm of origin.

Large volumes of data are collected frequently, necessitating a number of technical challenges (e.g. security, access, logging data). Sweden has a goal to make automatic processing and the production of reports more streamlined, while Denmark is working on a system to allow academics to access data without being given access to the main database. Governance through different devolved administrations in the UK makes data sharing more complicated as different organisations may operate different kinds of databases with different data formats. Conversations around the interpretation of data rules (which currently differ among devolved countries) are ongoing.

Exercise 2: Introduction to DigiVet tools

Participants were divided into groups and given the opportunity to familiarise themselves with one or both of the tools (depending on their interest/relevance to each participant). Their comments were captured, and are summarised below.

sdbuscontrol

The screenshots illustrate the sdbuscontrol web application interface, showing the introduction, input parameters for the cattle herd population, input parameters for the diagnostic tests, and the resulting herd level classifications.

Introduction

The sdbuscontrol package is meant as a tool to support decisions on a surveillance control program for *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle.

In the current setup the surveillance programme in the package classifies cattle herds into Level 1 (probably not infected with *Salmonella* Dublin) and Level 2 (probably infected with *Salmonella* Dublin) and the package outputs a sensitivity and specificity for this classification assuming a true infection prevalence.

The package allows the user to input a cattle herd population with specified herd types (e.g. Dairy herd) and herd sizes. This is done in the menu 'Cattle population'. Data on the cattle herd population may be uploaded directly or may be simulated from summary data.

Subsequently the user may choose what tests for *Salmonella* Dublin to include in the surveillance program. This is done in the menu 'Diagnostic tests'. The current version of the package includes animal blood samples, samples taken at clinical suspicion of *Salmonella* Dublin and bulk tank milk samples. For each test type the sensitivity and specificity may be adjusted. Furthermore, the user may specify how often different herd types or age-groups are sampled.

Finally, the package output how herds are classified into Level 1 and Level 2 given the above inputs and a true infection prevalence.

Input parameters for the cattle herd population

Option 1: Upload cattle herd population data

Upload a file

Option 2: Simulate cattle herd population

Enter herd population size

Please indicate how you prefer to provide data on herd type and herd size distributions

Enter data manually

Fill values in the below table

HerdTypeID	HerdTypeText	TypePrp	CattleNum_mean	CattleNum_std	InfPrp_mean	InfPrp_std	CalfPrp_mean	CalfPrp_std
1	Dairy	0.275	5400	670	0.207	0.204	0.202	0.207
2	Heifer	0.058	4300	570	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
3	Heifer mixed supply	0.058	3240	324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
4	Beef	0.500	2404	240	0.207	0.204	0.204	0.202
5	Veal	0.100	2279	228	0.207	0.204	0.204	0.202
6	Type missing	0.008	2275	228	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Population demographics

Head of cattle herd population data

HerdID	HerdTypeText	CattleNum	InfPrp	InfPrp_max	CalfPrp	CalfPrp_max
Herd_1	Beef	5520	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Herd_2	Type missing	3030	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Herd_3	Beef	500	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Herd_4	Veal	4400	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Herd_5	Dairy	5600	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Herd_6	Beef	2040	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Herd type distribution

Dairy

Heifer

Input parameters for the diagnostic tests

Antibody test on animal blood samples

Enter blood sample sensitivity

0.8

Enter blood sample specificity

0.98

Include sampling of slaughter in the program

Include sampling of heifers in the program

Include sampling of calves in the program

Include sampling of animals in health control centres or heifers in the program

Include voluntary sampling in the program

Enter serological culture on clinical samples

Enter culture sensitivity

0.8

Enter culture specificity

0.98

Enter probability of observing clinical signs indicating *S. Dublin* in an infected herd

0.1

Enter probability of observing clinical signs indicating *S. Dublin* in a non infected herd

0.02

Bulk tank milk samples

Enter milk sample sensitivity

0.98

Enter milk sample specificity

0.98

Enter the probability of bulk tank milk being sampled for each herd type

HerdTypeText	probSample
Dairy	1
Heifer	0
Heifer mixed supply	0
Beef	0
Veal	0
Type missing	0

Herd level classifications resulting from the surveillance program

Salmonella Dublin prevalence

Set true herd level prevalence for *S. Dublin*

0.1

Set within farms level prevalence for *S. Dublin*

0.1

Additional inputs

Classify non-sampled herds as Level 2

Enter number of sampling periods

1

Output surveillance classifications

Overall herd levels

SDLevelText	Non infected	Infected
Level 1	934 (95 %)	9 (6 %)
Level 2	47 (5 %)	142 (34 %)

Number of herds sampled in the last period

HerdTypeText	Sampled	Not sampled
Dairy	994 (200 %)	101
Heifer	3 (4 %)	74 (36 %)
Heifer mixed supply	2 (2 %)	90 (36 %)
Beef	72 (3 %)	2669 (91 %)
Veal	30 (3 %)	956 (97 %)
Type missing	11 (2 %)	531 (94 %)

Potential use

The sdbuscontrol package is a tool to support decision makers e.g., authorities in making decisions on the surveillance program for *S. Dublin* in cattle. This could for instance be decisions on what diagnostic tests to include in surveillance, which herd types or animal groups to sample and decisions on sampling frequency.

However, workshop participants representing Danish authorities suggested that the tool should be made as broadly applicable as possible. This led to a discussion on other contexts for which the tool could be developed. The discussion included use by veterinarians, use by farmers and generalization to use for other diseases, as elaborated in separate sections below.

Additionally, it was speculated whether the tool could be used in reverse to estimate diagnostic test sensitivities and specificity based on an inferential method that uses the tool to generate data given different assumptions, and evaluating which of these assumptions generates a simulated surveillance outcome that is closest to that observed in reality.

Use by veterinarians

Workshop participants from SEGES stated that they received inquiries from veterinarians on how many samples to take at a given point in the process of herd level eradication. Thus, the tool could be developed to support decision on sampling strategies during herd-level eradication.

Use by farmers

Workshop participants emphasized that it is difficult to motivate affected farmers for herd-level eradication. Therefore, participants discussed different applications for motivating farmers. These included some kind of visualization for the eradication process with a sampling regime and an expected development of within herd prevalence over time. It was also suggested to visualize the process of other farmers that previously succeeded in eradication or enabling a comparison between farmers.

The discussion on usability for the farmers resulted in suggestions to include the effect of different control measures or changes in herd size on disease spread within and between herds and additionally a cost-benefit analysis in the tool. However, for the farmer-specific purposes, workshop participants emphasized that the tool should not include options to change inputs due to the complexity of understanding the full implications of these inputs. Alternatively, veterinarians or other advisors should mediate the use of the tool for the farmers. Additionally, the tool should primarily output visualizations instead of numbers. As an additional means to motivate farmers there was a suggestion to give farmers a better insight into the development of *S. Dublin* on a national level through webinars.

General surveillance program

To increase usability of the tool, for instance in the UK where *Salmonella* Dublin is not a specific target for surveillance, a suggestion was to generalize the tool to be applicable for any disease, as the setup with diagnostic tests, sampling groups and sampling frequencies is universal.

Technical features

In addition to the discussion on potential use, workshop participants suggested a series of new technical features that might be useful to include in the tool, as follows:

- Clear visualization of false positive and false negative herds
- Ability to set true prevalence to zero
- More explanatory text like 'This is an average, which can be interpreted/used as ...'
- Stratification on herd size groups and risk groups
- Implement animal movements, including exports
- Avoid excessive complexity in the population input
- Provide more flexibility than just the predefined scenarios
- Include a reset button

These technical suggestions will be taken on board for future development of the tool.

goldeneye

<p>goldeneye Instructions Profile Encrypt File(s) Decrypt File(s)</p> <h3>Instructions</h3> <p>The goldeneye package is designed to facilitate easy encryption/decryption of potentially sensitive data. This shiny app is designed to make some of the features of the package available to those that do not use R. If you are a confident R user, then you can use the functions <code>gy_save</code> and <code>gy_zip</code> directly.</p> <p>Otherwise, please follow the steps below to set up an encryption profile, encrypt files, and decrypt files. You can return to these instructions at any time by clicking the "Instructions" tab above.</p> <h4>Step 1: Profile Setup</h4> <p>Click on the "Profile" tab to start.</p> <p>The first time you run this app you will need to set up a goldeneye profile (unless you already have a valid profile from previously using goldeneye/goldfinger encryption) - to do this, select "Create New" and enter the details requested. Note that the password and re-typed password must match. It is also VERY important that you do not forget your password! Once you have entered your details you can click on "Create Profile". You should then get a message that your profile was created successfully. <u>After this, you should click the link to download your new private key file. Save this file in a safe place.</u></p>	<p>goldeneye Instructions Profile Encrypt File(s) Decrypt File(s)</p> <p>Select goldeneye profile to use:</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Saved: md@sund.ku.dk</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Select Other</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Create New</p> <p>Profile and password are valid</p> <p>Download Public Key File</p>
<p>goldeneye Instructions Profile Encrypt File(s) Decrypt File(s)</p> <p>Select the file(s) to encrypt</p> <p><input type="button" value="Browse..."/> <input type="text" value="No file selected"/></p>	<p>goldeneye Instructions Profile Encrypt File(s) Decrypt File(s)</p> <p>Upload file to decrypt</p> <p><input type="button" value="Browse..."/> <input type="text" value="No file selected"/></p> <p>No file selected</p>

Potential use

The goldeneye tool is an encryption package that uses an open-source encryption library (libsodium; <https://libsodium.org>) to secure data so that it can only be used by specifically targeted individuals, using a combination of symmetric and asymmetric keys generated by the tool for specific users. The tool can encrypt/decrypt either objects stored within the R programming language (<http://cran.r-project.org>) or within one or more files stored on the hard drive. Usage of goldeneye was demonstrated to the participants using the dashboard interface.

General comments on goldeneye

The participants remarked that the goldeneye tool is simple and useful tool to support academia and research in the sharing of data. Of particular interest was the 'kill switch' function, which is designed to allow decryption access to be revoked by the owner of the data following the planned expiry date of the project (or sooner, if circumstances change during the project period). The participants remarked that this could be very useful for 'end of life' data projects as it is reassuring that data could no longer be accessible from a pre-determined date, and data sharing agreements could be signed with a stipulation of when data would automatically be deleted by the tool. Suggestions for additional features included the ability to include an end date for the project (after which decryption would no longer be allowed) within the provided interface.

Potential technical issues with the tool included the potential need to provide updates in future to accommodate changing features in R and underlying packages, and who would be responsible for this long-term maintenance of the package so that information held in encrypted data is not lost

over time. The project team noted that the goldeneye package has already been embedded within data workflows more widely at the University of Copenhagen, so maintenance of the package will be undertaken as part of routine duties (with funding implicitly provided by the University of Copenhagen). However, as with all software, it is impossible to guarantee that the software will function indefinitely.

The point was also made that, as with all data sharing, a key issue is trust: while the tool will keep data (and researchers) safe as long as they follow the guidelines provided with the tool, it is not infallible against misuse. For example, someone could bypass the encryption function of the tool and store the unencrypted data elsewhere, so the importance of trust still remains, even when the tool is used. It was noted that industry use of farmers' data is based on the farmers' trust in how they use these data. *Salmonella* Dublin is a good example of an application where the underlying data are considered too sensitive to be made publicly available, but where a desire exists for collaboration between industry and academic partners. It was felt that the goldeneye tool provides a much-needed layer of additional security in this case.

Next steps

The feedback provided by participants on both tools will be taken into consideration, and the tools will be adapted to include these suggestions where feasible. For the goldeneye tool we anticipate that including the suggestion to include an end date by default is quite feasible within a 6-9 month period. Some of the suggestions regarding the sdbuscontrol tool would require a substantial amount of work, but the more feasible suggestions will be incorporated in the medium term.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Participant affiliations

Denmark: Fifteen stakeholders participated from Denmark, ten female and five male

- Five from the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (FVST).
- One from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU).
- One from Statens Serum Institute (SSI).
- Four from SEGES Innovation.
- Four from the University of Copenhagen.

Sweden: Two female stakeholders participated from Sweden

- Both from the Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA).

UK: Three stakeholders participated from the UK, two female and one male

- One from the University of Glasgow.
- One from the Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA).
- One from Scotland's Rural College (SRUC).

Appendix 2: DigiVet project partners and contact details

DENMARK	Matt Denwood	University of Copenhagen	md@sund.ku.dk
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UK	Orla Shortall	James Hutton Institute	orla.shortall@hutton.ac.uk

Appendix 3: Summarised challenges and strengths by country

Table 1: Challenges in data use digitalisation for S. Dublin

Country group	Data Acquisition (connectivity, wearables, electronic identification, decision-support tools, diagnostics etc.)	Data Aggregation and Enrichment (data handling, interoperability, harmonisation etc.)	Data Management and Maintenance (partitioning, access, security etc.)	Data Usage and Return Value (Costs, relevance, user-friendliness, trust, transparency etc)
UK	No statutory surveillance systems for S. Dublin. A passive surveillance system is in operation.	There is ambiguity over whether the county parish holding number identifier counts as personal data.	<p>GDPR has made data sharing more difficult and time consuming.</p> <p>Data management and sharing is difficult between the four devolved nations.</p> <p>Data sharing agreements are ad hoc.</p> <p>Academics find it difficult to access data that they would like.</p>	
Denmark			<p>Data sharing challenges remain, especially between industry and academic partners.</p> <p>Data sharing agreements are ad hoc.</p>	<p>The public availability of sensitive farm level data is a potential issue.</p> <p>Storage of data on university servers is an issue because this makes it subject to freedom of information requests.</p>
Sweden	The uptake of voluntary routine testing of milk is somewhat limited.	Data exist in different formats which make them difficult to integrate.	<p>Data sharing is becoming more difficult.</p> <p>Data sharing agreements are ad hoc.</p>	

Table 2: Strengths in data use digitalisation for S. Dublin

Country group	Data Acquisition (connectivity, wearables, electronic identification, decision-support tools, diagnostics etc.)	Data Aggregation and Enrichment (data handling, interoperability, harmonisation etc.)	Data Management and Maintenance (partitioning, access, security etc.)	Data Usage and Return Value (Costs, relevance, user-friendliness, trust, transparency etc)
UK				Anonymised S. Dublin data from reference laboratories are used by academics.
Denmark	There is a statutory surveillance system for S. Dublin.		There is strong collaboration between industry, public bodies and academia on data management.	There is trust in the Danish system in relation to the management and use of data.
Sweden	There is a statutory surveillance systems for S. Dublin.		Data exist in different formats which make them difficult to share. There is a goal to make automate data processing and reporting.	Data on S. Dublin status at farm level is not publicly available, there is a desire to keep this private to protect farmers.

Digivet: digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

Workshop Information sheet 2023

We would like to invite you to a workshop about digitalisation of livestock data, including stakeholders from the UK, Sweden, and Denmark. It is part of a project called “Digivet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”. The workshop is undertaken by researchers at the University of Copenhagen in conjunction with partners at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, James Hutton Institute, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute. The project is funded by Nordforsk: a body which funds Nordic research and cooperation. The aims of the workshop are to:

- 1) Discuss the practical, ethical and governance issues surrounding the use and distribution of livestock data between industry and academic partners, including particular issues relating to potentially sensitive data.
- 2) Receive feedback on two data digitalisation tools developed in the Digivet project, relating to control strategies for Salmonella Dublin in cattle and sharing sensitive data using encryption.
- 3) Discuss the ethical and governance issues around the use of these tools and sharing data.
- 4) Share experiences about the use of similar data between stakeholders from the UK, Denmark, and Sweden.

Participants’ data will be stored securely and will only be accessible to the project team for the purposes of organising the workshop. The workshop will be conducted under the Chatham House Rule i.e. we will make notes of discussion topics during the workshop and produce a report which will be circulated to attendees, but these notes/report will NOT reveal the identity or affiliation of individuals in relation to specific comments.

If you wish to ask us any questions before deciding whether to take part, please contact us by email on: md@sund.ku.dk

Your participation is voluntary and you may leave the meeting at any time. All data collected will be treated with full confidentiality and in line with relevant data protection legislation.

Many thanks in advance for your participation,

Professor Matt Denwood (University of Copenhagen)

Title of Project:	Digivet: digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health
Principal Investigator:	Matt Denwood

Please Initial Box

I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and these have been answered fully and explicitly.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time before data is analysed and included in research outputs, without providing any reason and without my legal rights being affected.	
I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from University of Copenhagen in conjunction with partners at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, James Hutton Institute, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute.	
I understand that confidentiality will be maintained at all times and it will not be possible to be directly identifiable by name from any publications/outputs, however it is possible that these could include references to my organisation/affiliation and my role.	
I agree to take part in the above workshop	
I agree to being contacted at a later date for being provided with updates and information on the project.	
I acknowledge that I have read and understood the privacy notice [overleaf].	

Name of Participant (please print)

Signature

Date

PI

Signature

Date

Privacy Notice

The University of Copenhagen (“us” or “we”) will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in this project **“Digivet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”** (“The Project”) in accordance with our privacy notice at <https://informationssikkerhed.ku.dk/english/protection-of-information-privacy/privacy-policy/>.

Our lawful basis for processing your personal data is that this is necessary for publicly funded research we undertake as a task in the public interest. We are the data controller for the personal data collected for the purposes of above project. We will collect and use personal data in line with relevant data protection legislation including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Notes will be taken from the workshop to allow us the best opportunity to retrieve information for our study. Personal data (names, contact details, job field/role) will be linked to consent forms, but contributions to the workshop will be recorded anonymously. All data will be stored in restricted access files on the server and/or secure cloud-based storage used by the University of Copenhagen and research partners at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, James Hutton Institute, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute.

Contributions to the workshop will be anonymised through removal of names and other directly identifying information and published only in summarised form. However, summaries and other research outputs may include information on respondent’s background (e.g., academic, regulatory, policy-related, industry) and/or some original wording may be retained therein through which the individual may be indirectly identifiable.

We may share pseudonymised transcripts with a professional transcriber who has an appropriate contract in place with the James Hutton Institute to ensure that participants’ data is held securely and protected adequately.

We will retain your personal data only for as long this is necessary to fulfil the purposes and produce outputs for the Project and will delete/destroy it afterwards. Our main privacy notice will explain what we do with personal data in more detail as well as your rights. Or, if you have any queries about your personal data you can contact us by email at md@sund.ku.dk

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